

Engagement Communication Plan

V1.0

Funaction

Aquatic fungal
biodiversity

FUNACTION — Aquatic FUNgal biodiversity: developing knowledge and strAtegies to inform ConservaTION priorities and measures

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MINISTRY OF RURAL AFFAIRS

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1 FRAMEWORK & SCOPE

1.1 Administrative information

Project	FUNACTION: Developing knowledge and strategies to inform conservation priorities and measures
Responsible	FUNACTION Engagement and Dissemination Committee (EDC) led by Isabel Fernandes and Monika Böhm
Deliverable	D2 Engagement Communication Plan (ECP)
Work package	WP5 - Making a “splash”: effective engagement, communication, and dissemination of information
Delivery date	4 June 2024
Availability	Public

Data Management Plan version history

Version	Date	Modification	Author(s)
1.0	4 June 2024	Initial document	ECP led by I. Fernandes and M. Böhm

DMC - Data and Digital Outputs Management Committee

Country	DMC member	Active date (start)
Portugal	Isabel Fernandes*	April 2023
USA	Monika Böhm*	April 2023
Switzerland	Andreas Bruder	April 2023
Germany	Hans-Peter Grossart	April 2023
Sweden	Jennifer Anderson	April 2023
Italy	Laura Garzoli	April 2023
Estonia	Veljo Kisand	April 2023

*Committee Co-Chair

1.2 Scope

The ECP

- Supports common understanding and expectations among Partners and associated teams for the management of internal and external communications.
- Serves as a tool to ensure FUNACTION meets consortium goals for internal and external communications.
- Provides a mutually agreed framework for communication action planning, follow up, and review.

1.3 Acronyms, abbreviations, & definitions

AF	Aquatic Fungi
CA	Consortium Agreement
DMC	Data and Digital Outputs Management Committee
DMP	Data Management Plan
ECP	Engagement Communication Plan
EDC	Engagement and Dissemination Committee
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IUCN	International Union for Conservation of Nature
IUCN SSC	Species Survival Commission of the IUCN
KBA	Key Biodiversity Areas
No.	Number
OC	Oversight Committee
Partner	Individual listed as main applicants in the funded project
RP	Responsible Partner
SG	Specialist Group
Team	Participants in FUNACTION, often (but not exclusively) supervised by a Partner
TBD	To Be Determined
WP	Work Package. Numbers as per funded proposal

2 EDC

2.1 Authority for formation

FUNACTION uses the management structure described in the funded project proposal and as outlined in the figure (right) wherein:

The Coordinator serves as the point of contact between Biodiversa+ and FUNACTION and has special oversight responsibilities, including chairing the OC and holding the tie breaking vote. The Deputy Coordinator supports the Coordinator in project leadership, and serves as acting-Coordinator if needed (e.g. acute illness). **All Partners and their teams will cooperate towards the management of the project.**

The Action and specific Work Package relevant to the EDC are as follows:

- Action 6.2 Engagement and Dissemination Committee (EDC): Engagement and Dissemination are critical components of FUNACTION. Each Partner country is represented on the EDC, which will oversee internal and external communications in addition to playing a key role in WP5.
- Work Package 5 Making a “splash”: effective engagement, communication, and dissemination of information.

2.2 Membership, responsibilities, and scope

FUNACTION, communication and outreach will be guided and governed by an Engagement and Dissemination Committee (EDC). The EDC will develop, implement, and update the FUNACTION Engagement Communication Plan (ECP), detailing the rules and norms for internal and external communications.

- The EDC is composed of (minimum) one representative from each Partner country.
- The EDC meets twice per year (virtually), with interim virtual meetings and digital communications as needed.
- The EDC is co-chaired by the Responsible Partners for WP5.

3 INTRODUCTION: OVERARCHING RULES, GOALS, & PHILOSOPHY

**“No one will protect what they don’t care about...”
Sir David Attenborough.**

The FUNACTION consortium has the goal to develop experiences and tools to enable the conservation of aquatic fungi (AF) across Europe. Included in this goal is a commitment to effectively engage with the interested public, stakeholders, and the scientific community to build awareness of aquatic fungal biodiversity, the vital roles AF play in maintaining healthy, functioning, and valuable ecosystems, and the need for AF conservation; a.k.a. to give people reasons to “care” about AF conservation.

Given that this is the first-ever effort to develop experiences and tools to enable the conservation of AF across Europe, a lot of this work is covering novel ground. To reflect the heterogeneity across Europe, and to unify experts with the various skills needed to achieve this goal, the FUNACTION consortium is also multi-institutional and multi-national. To ensure dissemination and uptake of the experiences and tools developed by FUNACTION, the project includes a specific WP and deliverables to engage with external parties, stakeholders and the general public (WP5).

The objective of this ECP is to outline the strategy for dissemination and communication activities carried out during the FUNACTION project. Through this ECP, we will increase the reach of FUNACTION’s scientific outcomes, engage with the public in innovative ways, fast-track inclusion of AF into the global conservation arena and build capacity for AF conservation. This document identifies the main objectives of the communication and dissemination activities, it defines the project identity and puts forward the actions targeted at our diverse audiences (**Section 4.2 Target audience**). For each audience, the communication channels and means, and the associate deliverables are described. For direct stakeholders including policy makers (see audience profile), the procedures for stakeholder mapping are detailed. The document further explains the processes for evaluating and monitoring the impact of the project, as well as the obligations and requirements for communication actions. The ECP and FUNACTION’s communication actions are strategically designed to “make a splash” for AF conservation!

Given the complexity of the FUNACTION consortium and our audiences, and given the goals of the project, exemplary communication is key to maximize the efficiency and reach of the project and its outputs. Communication therefore needs to be planned, structured, monitored, and evaluated throughout the lifetime of the project. We distinguish two categories of communication: external communication (**Section 4 External communication plan**), i.e., with external entities including other projects, networks, stakeholders, the interested public, and other external audiences; and internal communication (**Section 5 Internal communication plan**), i.e., among Partners and their teams. Both categories of communication are described in this ECP. For each category and target audience, the ECP addresses the purpose of the outreach, the audience for the outreach, the messages to be shared, the methods for sharing the messages, the timing for the outreach, and the process for evaluating the success of the dissemination effort.

Note that this is a “living” document that can and will be modified as needed through the project’s lifetime.

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3.1 Transfer, dissemination, publication, and protection of results generated in the project

Transfer and dissemination of data and results (pre-publication) must be cleared by the EDC prior to sharing (except lectures and presentations). Requests will be evaluated from a position of supporting scientific progress without damaging/risking FUNACTION Partner studies and impact. Publications and reports resulting from FUNACTION will be submitted to the best suited, most visible journals for their respective topics, that adhere to applicable open access guidelines. Reporting to Biodiversa+ and national funding organisations will also be facilitated by the EDC. Authorships will follow FUNACTION’s publication guidelines (in preparation) developed following current norms, including substantial direct involvement in conception and planning, data generation and analyses, writing/critically revising, final draft approval and accountability. Inclusivity is encouraged to promote career development and retention of qualified scientists.

3.2 Inclusive communication

FUNACTION is committed to the use of inclusive communication to make sure no one is left behind. Inclusive communication includes the principles of Diversity, Equity, Belonging and Inclusion (El-Amin 2022). These principles should be respected in internal as well as external communication, although they might manifest differently according to these categories.

D
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Y Diversity refers to ethnicity/racial identity, sex, sexual orientation, gender identity, gender expression, physical diversity and neurodiversity, national origin, ideology, religion, family situation, age or socio-economic status, among others.

FUNACTION team members will use, to the best of their capacities, inclusive language (e.g., gender-inclusive language). This will be applied to any type of communication, whether it is oral or written, formal or informal, or addressed to an internal or external audience. Different contents will be produced that are suitable to the age range of the target audience. Finally, supporting materials (e.g., 3D models, see **Section 4.5.6 Other digital promotional and educational materials**) will be developed to promote access of visually impaired people to our communications about AF.

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Y Equity ensures that everyone has access to the same opportunities, resources, and information, regardless of their diversity background, career stage, research setting, etc. To be equitable, we aim to make publicly available all FUNACTION outputs that are aimed at broad external audiences (beyond internal communication with Partners) (**Section 4.5 Online dissemination tools**), to ensure access by everyone interested. Also, some outputs (**Section 4.6 Offline/hybrid dissemination tools**) will be produced in the different languages used in FUNACTION Partner countries to increase access to these resources.

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N Inclusion ensures everyone is treated fairly and respectfully. This principle will be applied in all communications including internal and external audiences, making sure everyone's perspective is heard and valued.

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G Belonging ensures a sense of value and that a person is needed and wanted. To achieve this, FUNACTION members will be actively encouraged to share ideas and inputs without judgement, and equal opportunities to lead particular tasks/projects will be provided. Special attention shall be given to early career researchers to make sure they feel valued and respected.

4 EXTERNAL COMMUNICATION PLAN

External communication serves as a portal of FUNACTION to a wider audience including stakeholders outside the project consortium. External communication tools and channels include the FUNACTION website, newsletters, social media (e.g., X, LinkedIn, YouTube).

FUNACTION adheres to the EU General Data Protection Regulation (EU GDPR). It is required that any personal data is collected and used for FUNACTION purposes only as outlined in the **FUNACTION Data Management Plan (DMP)**.

4.1 Communication Strategy

The FUNACTION communication strategy is based on three pillars which encapsulate different levels of knowledge and engagement by our audiences:

1) FUNACTION raises awareness & excites interest

The target audience does not need to have detailed knowledge; instead, communications are aimed at those with an interest in project activities (e.g. interested public). We will use communications and tools that mostly help to **Inform** about the FUNACTION project, via outreach materials, outreach events (in particular finding hooks using recognized milestones within the UN International days and weeks calendar), website, social media, e-newsletter (posted on website and advertised).

2) FUNACTION increases knowledge

The target audience has a deeper understanding of the project as interested parties who work in the same field, can benefit from project outcomes, or have the power to incorporate the project results (e.g. public administration, scientific community, policy makers/stakeholders). We will use communications and tools that mostly help to **Consult** with and **Involve** interested parties, such as e-newsletter, email, workshop, FUNACTION Masterclass and its portfolio of lessons (implemented in relation to Partners and stakeholders needs), presentations at conferences.

3) FUNACTION promotes & supports engagement & bidirectional knowledge transfer

Detailed and directed information is required by and from the target audience, with the communications and tools tailored to the respective goal of the engagement and audience in question. We will use communications and tools mostly to **Inform** and **Collaborate**, such as FUNACTION Masterclasses.

To ensure global awareness of project outputs beyond Partner countries and European borders, we will mobilize the EDC and Consortium to:

i) amplify the project using a dedicated FUNACTION website, social media profiles (X, LinkedIn, YouTube) and individual accounts (see **Section 4.5 Online dissemination tools**),

ii) submit press releases to institutional Public Relations offices, online science news outlets (e.g. popsci.com), and interested stakeholders (see **Section 4.6 Offline/hybrid dissemination tools**).

4.2 Target audiences

Communication activities will be tailored according to the various target audiences identified, and levels of engagement will differ between them, depending on audience and timing within the project. Different levels of engagement are identified, depending on the ultimate aims of the engagement activities and the project (**Durham et al. 2014**), from Inform (lowest level of engagement), via Consult and Involve (middle levels of engagement), to Collaborate (highest level of engagement).

FUNACTION target audiences have been clustered into the following categories: interested public, stakeholders (incl. policy makers), scientific and academic community, conservation community (see Tables below).

Table 1: Audience profiles for FUNACTION	
1a. Interested Public	
Objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increase public awareness about diversity and importance of AF in freshwater ecosystems
Approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Social media: X, LinkedIn, YouTube. Production of education materials and learning tools that support inclusive and accessible engagement across a range of sensory abilities, languages, and ages: infographics, short videos, and info sheets on key messages, avoiding jargon and explaining the complexity of AF diversity and its importance in simple and entertaining ways. Learning tools will include a memory card game, a kahoot quiz, and digital models of AF for 3D printing (valuable for the visually impaired). Participation in local outreach events: e.g. SciFest, Uppsala, GreenDay in Switzerland, International Day for Biological Diversity, European Researchers Night. Press releases to and articles/content in relevant national and local media (print, radio, television, web-based).
Engagement level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Inform</i>
Audience profiles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Students of diverse ages and stages. Local people living nearby or inside the case study protected areas. Citizens located near Partner institutions. Generally interested people.

1b. Stakeholders (incl. policy makers)	
Objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase stakeholders' awareness about the diversity and importance of AF in freshwater ecosystems. • Promote engagement toward the protection of AF in planning and management. • Collaborate with the managers of protected areas to select study sites and/or to formalize authorization for sampling. • Co-production of the first ever guidance for AF monitoring. • Provide recommendations addressed to policy makers, relevant institutions, and the public bodies at local, national and European levels to develop national/ international policies and strategic plans for AF conservation.
Approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Virtual roundtable discussions with interested stakeholders from each European Partner country to identify their needs and expectations for AF monitoring tools and guidance. • Engage in 2 rounds of iterative revision (to avoid stakeholder burnout) with the stakeholders to co-produce the first ever guidance for AF monitoring. • Virtual/in person FUNACTION Master Class series, including lessons and training courses for stakeholders (led by FUNACTION experts or specific knowledge-holders, incl. IUCN and GCSS representatives), to assure engagement and a bi-directional communication and knowledge-transfer. Events are planned throughout the whole project lifespan in correspondence to our main achievements and to present our results. Masterclasses will also cover == sampling and data handling protocols, with additional topics based on stakeholder and Partner needs and requests. • High-level events (FUNACTION midterm and final conference). • Communication materials. • Website. • Information dissemination via: Dedicated Freshwater Information Platform Atlas, reports, policy briefs. • Social media: X, LinkedIn, YouTube. • Press releases to and articles/content in relevant national and local media (print, radio, television, web-based). • Newsletter.
Engagement level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Inform, Consult, Involve, Collaborate</i>
Audience profiles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local and regional Protected Areas and resource managers. • Environmental protection agencies. • National/regional public administration. • Representatives of EU working groups: Microbial Resource Research Infrastructure – European Research Infrastructure Consortium (MIRRI-ERIC), and authorities representing indigenous Sami Villages within the target watersheds. • Representatives of EU Working groups on specific EU Directives (Habitat Directive, Water Framework Directive - WFD, Drinking Water Directive - DWD). • Representatives of the European Environment Agency's European Topic Centre on Inland, Coastal and Marine waters (ETC/ICM), European Commission Joint Research Centre, European based Freshwater Information Platform. • Global stakeholder organisations namely the International Mycological Association-IMA), hosts of taxonomic databases incl. Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) and UNITE. • Global/Regional policy-relevant networks and organisations coordinating biodiversity observations and conservation and supporting policy incl. Group on Earth Observations Biodiversity Observation Network (GEO BON), Freshwater Biodiversity Observation Network (FWBON) and International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN). • Local, National and EU policy makers.

1c. Scientific and academic community	
Objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maximize the reach of FUNACTION outputs and gain traction and recognition in freshwater and conservation fields. • Establish new collaborations to amplify FUNACTION outputs and to build the foundation to support future funding and projects.
Approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publication of papers in highly visible international peer-reviewed journals (prioritising open access journals and depositing data into publicly available repositories). • Attendance of scientific conferences (national and international). • High-level events (FUNACTION midterm and final conference). • Website. • Social media: X, LinkedIn, YouTube. • Newsletter. • Press releases to and articles/content in relevant national and local media (print, radio, television, web-based). • FUNACTION Master Class series.
Engagement level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Inform, Consult, Involve, Collaborate</i>
Audience profiles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • University research groups. • Public and Private Research Centers. • R&D groups in private companies. • Scientific communities & Expert boards.

1d. Conservation community	
Objective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide regular project updates and news to the conservation community. • Liaise with the IUCN Species Survival Commission to establish communication channels about AF to relevant Specialist Groups and Conservation Committees. • Spread outputs and lessons learned from FUNACTION to a global community interested in AF conservation.
Approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publication of papers in highly visible international peer-reviewed journals (prioritising open access journals and depositing data into publicly available repositories). • Attendance of scientific conferences (national and international) and conservation gatherings (e.g. IUCN SSC meetings). • Website. • Social media: X, LinkedIn, YouTube. • Newsletter. • Press releases to and articles/content in relevant national and local media (print, radio, television, web-based). • FUNACTION Master Class series.
Engagement level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Inform, Consult</i>
Audience profiles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conservation organisations & individual conservationists (especially those with a freshwater interest). • IUCN Species Survival Commission and its network (especially IUCN SSC Aquatic Fungi Specialist Group; IUCN SSC Freshwater Conservation Committee; IUCN SSC Fungal Conservation Committee; IUCN SSC Conservation Planning Specialist Group). • IUCN Red List & KBA communities

4.3 Key messaging

The following key communication messages should be considered in external communication. They are formulated in a way to be suitable for snap-shot communication towards the scientific and general public. They reflect the main goals and outputs of FUNACTION. They might be modified for specific communication.

“The biodiversity of aquatic fungi is largely unknown. This precludes conservation action for this crucial organism group. FUNACTION will make a start towards changing this.”

This message sets the stage, states the main knowledge gap addressed by FUNACTION. It also accounts for the fact that FUNACTION by itself will not be able to develop the entire basis needed for conservation of AF.

“The protected areas in your region might not have been designed with aquatic fungi in mind, but they could still support the biodiversity and conservation of aquatic fungi.”

This message is related to one of the main goals of FUNACTION, i.e. to evaluate the efficacy of current protected areas (e.g. national parks) to conserve and support AF biodiversity. This message can be addressed to the local stakeholders and public in the various regions covered by FUNACTION.

“Approaches and tools for the conservation of aquatic fungi are not yet available and need to be developed. FUNACTION will make the first steps towards this goal”.

This message refers to the concepts, approaches and tools that need to be developed for the conservation of AF. Concepts established by IUCN and other conservation entities have not been specifically designed for microscopic organisms, like AF, and do not account for their particular biology and ecology compared to other organisms. FUNACTION collaborates with the IUCN Biodiversity Assessment and Knowledge, Science and Data Centre (especially the IUCN’s Freshwater Lead), the IUCN SSC Aquatic Fungi Specialist Group, the IUCN SSC Fungal Conservation Committee, and if relevant with the IUCN SSC Standards and Petitions Committee, to evaluate their concepts, approaches, and tools and develop them to be applicable to AF.

Additional key messaging will be developed throughout the project by the EDC, in relation to latest project achievements, deliverables and news, and disseminated to the partner networks and relevant audiences as well as included in future versions of the ECP.

4.4 FUNACTION visual identity

The visual identity of FUNACTION was developed by Max Fonseca (expert in visual communication, SUPSI, Switzerland) and it includes the logotype, lettering and colour pantone.

Logotype: The logotype was a result of a combination of several concepts connected with the objectives of FUNACTION namely Fungi, Live, Organic, Environment, Aquatic, Fluid, Research, Conservation, Solid. Logo usage context varies by medium. Alternative versions aim to anticipate issues in small formats. The version most suited to the medium for legibility and recognizability should be chosen.

Preferred versions

These versions should be used whenever possible. The minimum height for use is 120 pixels.

Secondary versions

These should be used when the logo must be applied in reduced dimensions.

Tertiary versions

These should be used when the logo application has to be done in a very small space.

Icons

These should be used for profile images, and other graphic media that need a logo without text.

Font: The font chosen for the logo and titles is Apfel Grotesk, licensed under the SIL Open Font Licence (<https://openfontlicense.org/>), designed by Luigi Gorlero. The font is available from <https://www.collettivo.it>. The following versions of the font can be used:

Regular – ideal for texts and subheadings

Fett – ideal for titles

Mittel – ideal for subheadings

Brukt – ideal for playful titles

Since Apfel Grotesk is not a font that has all the Glyphs and also lacks the italic variation (needed for scientific names of organisms, for example), it should ideally be used only for headings and subheadings. Body text should be written with Roboto or Arial.

Note: Roboto font is available for Word processing software such as Microsoft Word and Google Docs. If it is not on your list of fonts in Google Docs, choose the "more fonts" option from the dropdown and find it there. Final formatting of the document can also be done on other software using Apfel Grotesk.

Colour pantone: The main version of the logotype in black should be used on white backgrounds. The white logotype versions are used for dark-coloured backgrounds.

Variations: The single-colour version of the logotype in black should be used with light-coloured backgrounds. Placing the logotype over complicated backgrounds should be avoided, since it might have a negative impact on proper readability.

Webpage accent colour: A yellow-green colour (see below) is used as an accent on www.funaction.eu. This colour is specified as follows:

4.5 Online dissemination tools (Digital visibility)

To promote visibility and inform on the project, the EDC will develop and maintain the FUNACTION logo, website, and social media accounts.

4.5.1 Website: A central hub for project information

The website (www.funaction.eu) will be the project's showcase for a broad audience to get information and updates. It will be developed at the beginning of the project and regularly updated with news and activities. A communication specialist will be involved to develop a pleasant, effective and attractive graphical interface. The purpose is to create a digital space to:

- Showcase the project's main objective.
- Showcase latest project achievements and news.
- Present the team and partnership.
- Act as an interactive platform to host the various digital products (papers, protocols, dissemination tools).

The website will be actively maintained for at least 1 year after the FUNACTION project lifetime, with a long-term plan for use of the webpage content developed in the After FUNACTION plan towards the end of the project.

4.5.2 Social media

Accounts will be created and maintained by EDC members on major social media networks to distribute information about the project and latest project news, spread key messages (see **Section 4.3 Key messaging**), issue project updates, link to communities of interest, and interact with potential stakeholders. Social media channels will allow the project to share catchy messages for quick communication and dissemination purposes and establish a virtual dialogue with relevant stakeholders, including appropriate projects/initiatives. The aim will be to raise awareness about the project for various stakeholders, update them on project advances, and to increase engagement with project outputs, including the FUNACTION website.

Social media in use: **X** **LinkedIn** **YouTube**

4.5.3 Promotion videos

Videos of the different project activities will be developed throughout the course of FUNACTION. They will be mainly distributed through social media as they will be the results of the different activities carried on by team members (both in field and in laboratory). Support by a professional visual communicator from SUPSI is available to produce this content. The purpose of the videos is to engage with the different audiences to:

- Raise curiosity about the topic of AF and their role in ecosystems.
- Highlight challenges and solutions related to AF conservation.
- Show the beauty and the aesthetic aquatic environments that the project aims to protect (cultural ecosystem services).

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4.5.4 Partners' websites and social media

Each Partner commits to broadcast project actions and results via their official channels (mainly website and social media). This will help magnify the impact of the project, while also giving recognition of Biodiversa+ partnership and funding agencies in Partners' official communication channels.

4.5.5 Newsletter: Regular updates for stakeholders

An E-newsletter will be published (at minimum) every year by EDC on the basis of information received from WP leaders, Partners, national funding organisations, Biodiversa+ partnership as well as stakeholders. The E-newsletters will be disseminated through the online newsletter facility “**Laposta.nl**”, which allows newsletter performances to be monitored through a graphical interface. These communications require the collection, use, and storage of personal data (name, organisation, and email) and will be undertaken according to the protocols for personal data in the **DMP** to respect GDPR requirements. Information for content of the newsletter will be solicited from Partners periodically and collected using appropriate means (e.g., Google Drive). The newsletter will also be deposited in the archive section of the project webpage.

4.5.6 Other digital promotional and education materials

The EDC will oversee the creation of additional learning tools for a range of sensory abilities, languages, and ages. It will include games and digital models, such as a printable memory card game, a kahoot quiz, and digital models of AF for 3D printing (valuable for the visually impaired). These materials and tools will be freely available for download through the FUNACTION website and will be shared with relevant organisations such as the IUCN SSC Aquatic Fungi Specialist Group (for use and/or adaptation to a global context).

4.6 Offline/hybrid dissemination tools

To facilitate innovative engagement, we will produce education materials that support inclusive and accessible engagement across a range of sensory abilities, languages, and ages.

4.6.1 Printed promotional and educational material

The production of printed promotional and educational material such as postcards and/or brochures which are translated into Partner country languages will widen the reach of our communication activities at specific physical events (especially conferences and stakeholder events), while printed infographics on AF and their role in ecosystems, and info sheets on key messages (see **Section 4.3 Key messaging**), can help increase awareness at public outreach events. These materials will avoid jargon and explain the complexity of AF diversity and its importance in simple and entertaining ways.

We will use these materials, in conjunction with relevant physical versions of promotional and educational materials mentioned in **Section 4.5.6 Other digital promotional and educational materials**, when we participate in local outreach events (e.g. SciFest, Uppsala, GreenDay in Switzerland, International Day for Biological Diversity, European Researchers Night). All tools will be freely available for printing through the FUNACTION website and will be shared with relevant organisations locally or regionally/globally (e.g., **IUCN SSC Aquatic Fungi Specialist Group**).

4.6.2 Press releases and press conferences

Press releases via Public Relations departments of Partner institutions will be issued throughout the project, to the extent possible, specifically when major project deliverables and milestones are met. Key milestones identified for potential press releases are:

- Specific events:
 - Project kick-off (mid 2023)
 - Mid-term conference/workshop (date TBD)
 - Final conference/workshop (date TBD)
- Publication of deliverables (dates TBD):
 - Creation of the first open-access pan-European database of AF biodiversity related to environmental metadata.
 - Evaluation report of the effectiveness of existing PAs for conservation of AF biodiversity.
 - Identification of the key drivers of AF alpha and beta diversity on the pan-European scale.
 - Map of AF biodiversity hotspots relative to the distributions of other aquatic eukaryotes.
 - Identification of regional and local drivers of AF biodiversity in relation to their ecosystem functions (publication in international peer-reviewed scientific journal).

- Publication of deliverables (continued)
 - Map of suggested PAs to conserve and maintain AF biodiversity (publication in international peer-reviewed scientific journal).
 - Description of the spatio-temporal relationships between AF biodiversity and functional diversity relative to protection status (publication in international peer-reviewed scientific journal/evaluation report).
 - IUCN Red List Assessments for AF taxa identifiable to species.
 - First ever guidance for AF monitoring.

Press releases will be drafted in English by the EDC and shared with Public Relations departments of Partner institutions. The EDC encourages Partner institutions to translate these press releases into their language, adapt the text where suitable to their national context, and highlight the role of their institution and the activities they contributed to FUNACTION to their version of the press release. This includes contributing photos and quotes relevant for the local institutes and context.

4.7 Events

4.7.1 Organisation of events

Two major events will be organised:

- **Mid-term conference/workshop** (hybrid) to communicate FUNACTION progress, involve and engage stakeholders, and support ‘next steps’ planning.
- **Final conference/workshop** (hybrid) to inform about FUNACTION outcomes to stakeholders including policy makers and the interested conservation community, and develop future plans for AF conservation. There is a possibility to include an open session at this event aimed at all audience groups, including the interested public. This would require adaptation of materials and language between open and expert sessions to suit the respective audiences.

In the run-up to these two events, we will also engage in virtual roundtable discussions with interested stakeholders, including interested policy makers and members of the conservation community, from each European Partner country to identify their needs and expectations for AF monitoring tools and guidance. All events will be advertised via our social media (see **Section 4.5.2 Social media**), e-newsletter (see **Section 4.5.5 Newsletter: Regular updates for stakeholders**), and/or directly via email.

In addition to these two major events, and to assure engagement and a bi-directional communication and knowledge-transfer, we will develop a virtual/in person FUNACTION Masterclass series, including lessons and training courses specifically aimed internally at our FUNACTION consortium and externally at our stakeholder, scientific and academic, and conservation community audiences (led by FUNACTION experts or specific external knowledge holders, incl. IUCN and GCSS representatives). We have planned events throughout the whole project lifespan to correspond with the skills sets covered by FUNACTION activities (e.g. conservation assessment, sampling, Key Biodiversity Areas (KBA) identification and development), and to present our main achievements and project results. Further targeted classes may be developed on the basis of stakeholders' requests. Online/hybrid Masterclasses will be recorded and shared online via the FUNACTION website/YouTube channel and/or Partner websites/YouTube channels (except when priority data and/or internal resources are included, e.g., FUNACTION protocols). The portfolio of Masterclasses will thus remain a lasting output from the project and source of guidance to AF practitioners and researchers.

Table 2. FUNACTION Events & Masterclasses already delivered & planned.

Event	Date	Format	Target Audience	Delivery date
Masterclass on Protocols for FUNACTION	Mid 2023	In person	FUNACTION consortium	August 2023
Masterclass on Systematic Conservation Planning	Early 2024	Virtual	FUNACTION consortium, Stakeholders, Conservation Community, Scientific & academic audience, IUCN SSC Aquatic Fungi SG, Interested public	March 2024
Masterclass on Red Listing	Mid 2024	Virtual	FUNACTION consortium, Stakeholders, Conservation Community, Scientific & academic audience, IUCN SSC Aquatic Fungi SG, Interested public	TBD
Mid-term conference/ workshop	September 2024	Virtual In person	FUNACTION consortium, Stakeholders	TBD
Masterclass on AF monitoring tools	May 2025	Virtual In person	FUNACTION consortium, Stakeholders, Conservation Community, Scientific & academic audience	TBD
Final conference/ workshop	February 2026	Virtual In person	FUNACTION consortium, Stakeholders, Conservation Community, Scientific & academic audience, IUCN SSC Aquatic Fungi SG, Interested public	TBD

4.7.2 Participation in external events

To enhance the reach of FUNACTION products, it is crucial to participate in external events. Types of external events that we are planning to participate in are listed in Table 3. The very different types of external events require specific and adapted communication and content. FUNACTION members are expected to bring upcoming external events to the attention of the EDC, which then decides on and coordinates participation as well as the most appropriate type of communication. Participation can be delegated to FUNACTION members that volunteer themselves. For in-person events, participation should be delegated whenever possible to local FUNACTION members to minimise long-distance travels. Participation needs to be evaluated against a cost-benefit-analysis (considering costs in terms of time, CO2-emissions, monetary costs, etc.). This is particularly important if no local members are available.

Table 3. Types of external events			
Type of event	Target audience	Regularity	Examples
Biodiversa+ workshops	Members of other projects, funding agencies	~ 1/year	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Capacity-building Webinar on Strengthening Science Policy Interface in support of the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) (June 2023) Capacity-building Webinar “Using social media - an introduction for scientists” (September 2023) Capacity Building Webinar - Policy Workshop session (Oct. 2023) Data management Workshop (BiodivProtect June 2023; J. Anderson invited presentation at BiodivMon June 2024)
Workshops/meetings of other projects	Members of other projects	unknown	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Biodiversa+ projects: INSPIRE, DARCO Cost Action: PARAQUA etc.
Scientific conferences	Scientific community, global stakeholders	~2/year	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> World Biodiversity Forum Congress of the International Society of Limnology (SIL) International Mycological Congress (IMC)
Local dissemination events	Interested public	Several per year	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GreenDay (CH) European Researchers Night (e.g. PT, IT, EE) SciFest (SE) Pint of Science (IT)

5 INTERNAL COMMUNICATION PLAN

The EDC coordinates internal communication to ensure effective communication among the FUNACTION Partners and team members (i.e., the consortium) throughout the project lifetime. Email will be the primary tool for official communication (e.g. announcements of Consortium meetings) and Element for text-based discussions, general notifications (including from the Coordinator), questions, messaging etc. It is expected that Consortium members stay current with the Element-based communications either through direct participation on Element or by arranging to be informed by a team member. Targeted and time-sensitive discussions should be organised via regular virtual meetings for the whole consortium and for the three committees (Oversight Committee (OC); Data and Digital Outputs Management Committee (DMC), and Engagement and Dissemination Committee (EDC)). These regular meetings can be complemented by virtual ad-hoc meetings when necessary.

5.1 Guidelines for internal communications

All internal communications should respect the high ethical standard that we have set for all interactions and communications of the project. In particular, they must use respectful, non-discriminating and inclusive language (see **Section 3.2 Inclusive communication**). This means they must be addressed at and involve all consortium members that have the right to be involved in the communication/discussion. Reasonable efforts should be made to have a record of communications (notes, emails, etc.). Any consortium member that feels excluded from communications that he/she/they have the right to be involved in should inform the Oversight Committee or a member thereof and request clarification.

5.2 Internal communication tools

Internal communications will be mainly based on regular online meetings, email exchange and our dedicated **Element** platform.

5.2.1 Consortium and committee meetings

Consortium meetings are a component of Consortium Governance and therefore follow the rules established in the FUNACTION Consortium Agreement (CA). Committee meetings are not subject to the same rules from the perspective of that document, however, the Committees may choose to adopt the same protocols.

In general, Consortium and committee meetings are prepared and announced by the coordinator of the respective group (OC, EDC, DMC). In the absence of the respective coordinator, this task can also be delegated to another consortium member. The coordinator of the consortium or the committee prepares an agenda of the upcoming meeting and circulates that among the participants at least 14 days before the meeting (5 days before an extraordinary meeting) unless otherwise agreed. At this stage, she/he/they also invite participants to propose additional agenda items. The coordinator of the meeting leads the discussion of the meeting following the agenda. She/he/they make reasonable efforts to end the meeting in the planned time. The coordinator of the meeting or an identified meeting participant develops written meeting minutes and makes them digitally available to the consortium or all participants of the respective meeting (e.g. in the case of a committee meeting) max. 10 calendar days after the meeting and invites written inputs and corrections to be provided within 15 days. After that, the minutes will be finalised by the coordinator and deposited on the FUNACTION google drive. Members of the consortium or the committee are expected to read the final version of the minutes and act upon the tasks defined during the meeting. This is particularly true for members that were unable to attend the meeting. It is not planned to video or audio record the meetings of the consortium or the committees.

5.2.2 Email exchanges

Emails are useful for small and specific exchanges. However, they are not suited for extended discussions. Often, they are also not inclusive or they are read with delay. They thus cannot replace discussions in **Element** or in the Consortium or committee meetings. Written discussions on Element are therefore to be preferred over email (see below). Consortium members are expected, as far as reasonably possible, to retain project-related emails and to share those emails with Consortium members with legitimate interest upon request by the EDC or OC.

5.2.3 Element

Element (<https://element.io/>) is a network communication and collaboration tool. This application features secure communications by using end-to-end encryption of messages, data sovereignty (we retain control and ownership of data), and a resilient structure to prevent system failures. The FUNACTION Space and Rooms have restricted access and the flexibility to add rooms for the discussion of new or specific topics. Further, in the free plan, there is no current data or time limit for retaining communications, and communications logs can be easily downloaded for backup ensuring retention of discussion and decision communications.

Written discussions on **Element** are preferred over email exchanges due to:

- The improved capacity for organisation, transparency, and inclusivity;
- Reduced data redundancy and storage (redundant data in the increasingly long email chains sent back and forth and multiply stored);
- The collection and retention in a single “location” for future consultation as needed (rather than individual email accounts) and backup of the communications.

In **Element** FUNACTION has a designated “Space” called “FUNACTION”. After individuals establish an account with Element, they can send their username to the Space administrator to be invited to join the Space. After joining the Space, individuals self-select to join the FUNACTION-associated “Rooms”. Rooms are designed to organise communications on particular topics. Note that i) rooms with restricted access (e.g. committees, WP leaders, etc.) can be created to support text-based discussion to reduce the information load and notifications to the whole Consortium; ii) all relevant Consortium members should be granted access to the restricted rooms, in compliance with FUNACTION’s inclusivity standards. When establishing a new room, it is preferred that the setting to ‘allow members to view history from the time of selecting this option’ is activated.

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6 EVALUATION & MONITORING OF DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

FUNACTION has the goal of effectively building interest, awareness, and involvement in AF conservation through its diverse communication and engagement activities in addition to achieving scientific impact. Thus, it is critical to employ approaches that allow the evaluation, monitoring, and improvement of the work to gauge progress towards these goals. Although there are no “perfect” or “one-size-fits-all” metrics of effectiveness in this context, monitoring and evaluating our engagement and communication activities with these overall goals in mind can support the following:

Focused planning to identify and achieve communication goals;

- Careful consideration of the needs of the activity-specific target audience(s) and best approaches for achieving the communication goals;
- Reflective practice, whereby we learn from the work and adjust future activities;
- Tracking and estimation of uptake and impact of communication and engagement activities;
- Adjusting communications and approaches to best reach target stakeholders.

6.1 Monitoring

Oversight of FUNACTION communications and engagement activities will rely on reporting to a centralised Dissemination Log (see **Section 6.3 Dissemination log**) as follows:

- Partner, Team, or Participant activities (e.g. lectures, press releases based on individual or local activity, local outreach activities, social media events that features FUNACTION activities) are self-reported. Note, spontaneous social media posts from individual Partner social media accounts are not reported.
- Consortium-level activities (e.g. website, official social media accounts, actions catalysed by the EDC, DMC, or OC, and deliverables) are reported by a designated representative or the activity-responsible person.
- Third-party coverage of FUNACTION. In the case that FUNACTION is covered by outside-of-project actors, and this comes to the attention of the EDC, they are responsible for reporting via a designated representative.

6.2 Evaluation

Evaluation of activity effectiveness takes place as follows:

- **Planning:** In cases where activity-specific feedback is sought, the feedback mechanism must be developed during activity planning.
- **Measurement:** Collection of available data as per Table 4, set up via a Google Form.

Continues on next page

- **Reflection:** Outcomes of Consortium-level events will be discussed by the EDC to determine if activity goals were achieved and to identify if/how similar future activities can be improved, with results noted in the EDC meeting notes. Other events will be reported in the Dissemination Log. These events will be discussed and noted by the EDC on a case-by-case basis with emphasis on learning-from or improving future activities.
- **Summary:** The EDC will summarise and report on the monitoring and evaluation processes and outcomes as part of the EDC mid-term and final reports, and briefly summarise activity evaluations in any relevant consortium meetings.

Table 4. Tools and measurement of success of the dissemination activities

Activity/Tool	Measurements and Summary counts
Scientific Talk Scientific Poster Public Lecture	Estimated audience size No. of participants/viewers/etc. if known No. of presentations by type Feedback (when relevant, e.g. post lecture survey)
Policy Documents Data release Other Resource Releases	No. of documents No. of downloads No. of citations at project completion (where applicable)
Publications in peer-reviewed journals	No. of publications Impact factor of journals No. citations at project completion
Website	No. visitors and trends in visitor traffic
X (social media platform)	No. impressions, likes, re-posts within 1 month (for specific activities/campaigns/posts) No. impressions, likes, re-posts (per month) No. of planned campaigns/posts No. followers/No. New followers per month
LinkedIn	No. page views (per month) No. followers/No. New followers per month No. impressions (per month)
YouTube	No. of subscribers No. views of webinar recordings
Radio, Television, Newspaper, Press Release, Blog Post, Other public text	Estimated audience size/reach Counts by type Geographic reach
Stakeholder Meeting, Masterclasses	Estimated audience size No. of live participants/viewers if known No. views/downloads of webinar recordings Feedback (e.g. survey)
Outreach Activities	Estimated audience size No. of participants/viewers/etc. if known Where relevant & only if possible, average length of time participants engaged with the activity Feedback (when relevant, e.g. post-event survey)

Table 4. continued

Activity/Tool	Measurements and Summary counts
Final Conference	Estimated audience size No. of participants/viewers/etc. if known No. views/downloads of webinar recordings (if relevant) Feedback (e.g. survey)
E-Newsletters	No. recipients (reported as No. of participants/viewers/etc. if known) and downloads
Project Documents (e.g. DMP, ECP)*	% of Partnership reached, downloads

* Internal communication

6.3 Dissemination Log

In order for the Consortium to be able to evaluate the effectiveness of the dissemination activities, it is crucial to monitor and keep track of the outcomes and outreach of the dissemination activities. For this purpose, a Dissemination Log will be created (Table 5).

Table 5. Dissemination Log (all applicable fields shall be filled)

Who	Team/group	FUNACTION, DMC, EDC, Estonia, Germany, Italy, Portugal, Sweden, Switzerland, USA, Third-Party
	Participant(s)	Name of the FUNACTION participants
What	Activity Type	Scientific Talk, Scientific Poster, Scientific publication, Public Lecture, Radio, Television, Newspaper, Other public text, Outreach Activity, Website, X, LinkedIn, YouTube, other Social media, Press Release, Policy document, Blog post, Stakeholder meeting, Survey, Masterclass, Newsletter, Data release, Other Resource Release
	Description (incl. title, conference title, as applicable)	
	Work Package	WP1-WP6, as or if appropriate
When	Date of activity	
Where	Place-geographical location	
	Place-journal or publication	
	Impact factor (if journal)	
Reach	Primary Stakeholder category	Interested Public (subcategories if applicable/necessary: youth, adult, mixed); Stakeholders (subcategories if applicable/necessary: Protected Areas and resource managers/agencies, National/regional public administration, Global and EU stakeholder groups and networks, Local/national/EU

7 OBLIGATIONS & REQUIREMENTS FOR COMMUNICATION ACTIONS

In order to brand the FUNACTION project, and to acknowledge the role of Biodiversa+ partnership and national funding organisations, all the project communication tools (brochures, flyers, posters, websites, videos, articles in scientific journals, books, etc.) should be prepared in accordance with the project brand identity guidance. Therefore, all project members are obliged to include in all Communication and Dissemination materials the following elements:

- FUNACTION logotype as described in **Section 4.4 FUNACTION visual identity**.
- Biodiversa+ logo, always together with the logo of the European Commission, and text “Funded by the European Union”, following the Biodiversa+ Guidelines for the acknowledgement of Biodiversa+ and the funding organisations of funded research projects. Biodiversa+ Guidelines are posted within Biodiversa+’s BiodivProtect_Follow-up-funded-projects/Tool_kit Dropbox. The link is posted within the Admin Room of the FUNACTION Element Space. This link is not public.
- Logotypes of FUNACTION funding organisations including both Biodiversa+ (below) and National funders (Table 6), according to their respective rules.
- The acknowledgment text required by Biodiversa+:

“This article/publication is based upon work from FUNACTION project, funded by Biodiversa+, the European Biodiversity Partnership under the 2021–2022 BiodivProtect joint call for research proposals, co-funded by the European Commission (GA N°101052342) and with the funding organisations: FORMAS, Sweden (2022-01701), Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia, Portugal (DivProtect/0007/2021); DOI: <https://doi.org/10.54499/DivProtect/0007/2021>; Schweizerischer Nationalfonds zur Förderung der Wissenschaftlichen Forschung, Switzerland (31BD30_209584), Ministry of Rural Affairs, Estonia (Ieping nr 95), Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft e.V., Germany (GR1540/47-1), Ministry of University and Research, Italy, and the Indianapolis Zoo.”
- Logotypes of FUNACTION Partner institutions according to their respective rules (see Table 7), if applicable. If a Partner institution has no specific rules, the correct logo must be used and permission must be sought for use of the logo. Each Partner/Team is responsible for ensuring that the logo and rules for its use are respected.

7.1 Open science data and intellectual property

FUNACTION is committed to use of Open Data and Open Access (OA) in respect to the FAIR data principle (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). Our scientific results will be primarily published giving preference to Gold and Green Open Access journals and making our data openly available for the scientific community, as also described in the **DMP**. Intellectual property of all the project members will be respected, as also described in the FUNACTION CA.

Table 6. List of FUNACTION funding organisations with links to logotype use rules

Partner Country	Link to funding agencies logotype use rules
Sweden	FORMAS
Portugal	Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia
Switzerland	Schweizerischer Nationalfonds zur Förderung der Wissenschaftlichen Forschung
Estonia	Ministry of Rural Affairs (link to be added)
Germany	Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft e.V.
Italy	Ministry of Universities and Research
USA	Indianapolis Zoo, Global Center for Species Survival (self-funded) – no specific rules

Table 7. List of FUNACTION Partner Institutions with links to logotype use rules

Partner Country	Link to Partner Institutions logotype use rules
Sweden	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences
Portugal	University of Minho Centre of Molecular and Environmental Biology
Switzerland	Scuola Universitaria Professionale della Svizzera Italiana (SUPSI)
Estonia	University of Tartu
Germany	Leibniz Institute of Freshwater Ecology and Inland Fisheries (IGB) - available to IGB members only
Italy	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
USA	Indianapolis Zoo, Global Center for Species Survival – no specific rules

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